

Table 1: A set of CNL statements from the four ontologies, with their corresponding verbalization using highlights. Statements introduced by the models that did not exist in the CNL statements (false positives) are highlighted with blue.

Ontology	CNL Statements (Input)	GPT-4o (Output)	Llama 3 (Output)
Pizza	margherita is a type of a named pizza. margherita is a type of at least has topping some a mozzarella topping. margherita is a type of at least has topping some a tomato topping. margherita is a type of only has topping any of (a mozzarella topping, and a tomato topping). margherita is different from (a la reine, and a frutti di mare, and a fiorentina, and a sloppy giuseppe, and an american hot, and a veneziana, and an unclosed pizza, and a mushroom, and a pollo ad astra, and a caprina, and a cajun, and an american, and a giardiniera, and a prince carlo, and a capricciosa, and a siciliana, and a parmense, and a rosa, and a soho, and a quattro formaggi, and a four seasons, and a napoletana).	Margherita is a distinct type of pizza, specifically characterized by its toppings of mozzarella and tomato. It exclusively features these two toppings and does not include any others. Moreover, Margherita is different from a variety of other pizzas, such as La Reine, Frutti di Mare, Fiorentina, Sloppy Giuseppe, American Hot, Veneziana, any unclosed pizza, Mushroom, Pollo ad Astra, Caprina, Cajun, American, Giardiniera, Prince Carlo, Capricciosa, Siciliana, Parmense, Rosa, Soho, Quattro Formaggi, Four Seasons, and Napoletana.	A Margherita pizza is a specific type of pizza that has at least one mozzarella topping and at least one tomato topping. It only has these two toppings - no others. This makes it distinct from other types of pizzas like La Reine, Frutti di Mare, Fiorentina, Sloppy Giuseppe, American Hot, Veneziana, Unclosed Pizza, Mushroom, Pollo ad Astra, Caprina, Cajun, American, Giardiniera, Prince Carlo, Capricciosa, Siciliana, Parmense, Rosa, Soho, Quattro Formaggi, Four Seasons, and Napoletana.
		TP: 4, FP: 0, FN: 1	TP: 4, FP: 0, FN: 1
People	nick carraway has age 28.	Nick Carraway is 28 years old.	Nick Carraway, the protagonist, has an age of twenty-eight years old.
		TP: 1, FP: 0, FN: 0	TP: 1, FP: 1, FN: 0
Mondo	euthyroid sick syndrome has definition a Abnormal thyroid function tests, low triiodothyronine with elevated reverse triiodothyronine, in the setting of non-thyroidal illness. euthyroid sick syndrome has exact synonym a sick euthyroid syndrome. euthyroid sick syndrome has exact synonym a sick-euthyroid syndrome. euthyroid sick syndrome has exact synonym an euthyroid sick syndrome. euthyroid sick syndrome is a type of a syndromic disease. euthyroid sick syndrome is a type of a thyroid gland disorder.	Euthyroid sick syndrome, also known as sick euthyroid syndrome, sick-euthyroid syndrome, or euthyroid sick syndrome, is characterized by abnormal thyroid function tests. These tests typically show low triiodothyronine (T3) and elevated reverse triiodothyronine (rT3) in the context of a non-thyroidal illness. This syndrome is classified as both a syndromic disease and a thyroid gland disorder.	Euthyroid sick syndrome, also known as sick euthyroid syndrome or sick-euthyroid syndrome, is an exact synonym for itself. It's a type of syndromic disease and a type of thyroid gland disorder characterized by abnormal thyroid function tests, low triiodothyronine levels, and elevated reverse triiodothyronine levels, typically occurring in the context of non-thyroidal illness.
		TP: 6, FP: 1, FN: 0	TP: 6, FP: 0, FN: 0
FMA	femoral nutrient artery is a type of a perforating femoral artery. femoral nutrient artery is a type of at least branch of some a deep femoral artery. femoral nutrient artery preferred name a Femoral nutrient artery.	The femoral nutrient artery is a type of perforating femoral artery and is also a branch of a deep femoral artery. Its preferred name is Femoral Nutrient Artery.	The femoral nutrient artery, also known as the Femoral nutrient artery, is a type of perforating femoral artery and is always a branch of a deep femoral artery, but it's not necessarily the only one.
		TP: 3, FP: 0, FN: 0	TP: 3, FP: 1, FN: 0

Table 2: Examples of verbalization of OWL statements as direct inputs with minimal pre-processing.

Ontology	OWL Statements (Input)	GPT-4o (Output)	Llama 3 (Output)
Pizza	<pre> 1 :margherita a owl:Class ; rdfs:subClassOf [a owl:Restriction ; owl:onProperty :has_topping ; owl:someValuesFrom :mozzarella_topping],[a owl:Restriction ; owl:onProperty :has_topping ; owl:someValuesFrom :tomato_topping],[a owl:Restriction ; owl:allValuesFrom [a owl:Class ;owl:unionOf [rdf:first :mozzarella_topping ; rdf:rest [rdf:first :tomato_topping ; rdf:rest :nil]]]; owl:onProperty :has_topping], :named_pizza ; owl:disjointWith :american, :american_hot, :cajun, ... </pre>	<p>The class "margherita" is defined as a type of pizza with specific characteristics. It must have at least some mozzarella topping and some tomato topping. Additionally, it can only have mozzarella and tomato toppings, and nothing else. "Margherita" is also a subclass of named pizza. Furthermore, it is explicitly distinct from a variety of other pizza types such as American, American Hot, Cajun, Capricciosa, Caprina, Fiorentina, Four Seasons, Frutti di Mare, Giardiniera, La Reine, Mushroom, Napoletana, Parmense, Pollo ad Astra, Prince Carlo, Quattro Formaggi, Rosa, Siciliana, Sloppy Giuseppe, Soho, Unclosed Pizza, and Veneziana.</p>	<p>A Margherita pizza is a type of pizza that must have mozzarella and tomato toppings, but it can also have other toppings. It's specifically not one of those other types of pizzas like American, American Hot, Cajun, Capricciosa, Caprina, Fiorentina, Four Seasons, Frutti di Mare, Giardiniera, La Reine, Mushroom, Napoletana, Parmense, Pollo ad Astra, Prince Carlo, Quattro Formaggi, Rosa, Siciliana, Sloppy Giuseppe, Soho, or Unclosed Pizza.</p>
Mondo	<pre> 1 :euthyroid_sick_syndrome a owl:Class ;rdfs:label "euthyroid sick syndrome" ; ns1:hasDbXref "DOID:2856", "EFO:1000931", "ICD10CM:E07.81", ... ns1:id "MONDO:0006755" ;ns1:inSubset :otar ; rdfs:subClassOf :syndromic_disease, :thyroid_gland_disorder ;skos:closeMatch :10015549 ; skos:exactMatch :237542005, :41908, ... ;:has_definition "Abnormal thyroid function tests, low triiodothyronine with elevated reverse triiodothyronine, in the setting of non-thyroidal illness." ; :has_exact_synonym "euthyroid sick syndrome", "sick euthyroid syndrome", "sick-euthyroid syndrome" </pre>	<p>Euthyroid sick syndrome is a type of disorder classified under both syndromic disease and thyroid gland disorder. It is identified with the database reference "MONDO:0006755" and is part of the OTAR subset. The syndrome has multiple database cross-references, including DOID:2856, EFO:1000931, ICD10CM:E07.81, ICD9:790.94, MEDGEN:41908, MESH:D005067, MedDRA:10015549, NCIT:C113170, SCTID:237542005, and UMLS:C0015190. In terms of matching, it has close matches with 10015549 and exact matches with 237542005, 41908, c0015190, d005067, doid 2856, e07.81, and ncitc113170. The disorder is characterized by abnormal thyroid function tests, specifically low triiodothyronine and elevated reverse triiodothyronine, in the context of non-thyroidal illness. It is also known by the synonyms "euthyroid sick syndrome," "sick euthyroid syndrome," and "sick-euthyroid syndrome."</p>	<p>Euthyroid Sick Syndrome is a type of syndromic disease that falls under Thyroid Gland Disorder. It's characterized by abnormal thyroid function tests, specifically low triiodothyronine levels with elevated reverse triiodothyronine levels, which occurs in the context of non-thyroidal illness. This condition has been linked to various medical concepts and databases, including DOID:2856, EFO:1000931, ICD10CM:E07.81, ICD9:790.94, MEDGEN:41908, MESH:D005067, MedDRA:10015549, NCIT:C113170, SCTID:237542005, and UMLS:C0015190.</p>

Table 3: Analysis of errors per model and axiom type.

Model	Error Type	Total	Associated Axiom	Count
GPT-4o	Concept renamed - the name of the concept was changed or rephrased	12	subClassOf	12
	Missing Relationship - Relationship that was completely omitted	12	allValuesFrom	3
			subClassOf	5
			someValuesFrom	3
			equivalentClass	1
	Replacement of relationship with a another relationship that has the same meaning	15	someValuesFrom	6
			disjointWith	2
			equivalentClass	3
			subClassOf	3
			-	1
Incorrect Relationship - relationship was replaced with one of a different meaning	1	someValuesFrom	1	
Incomplete Decomposition	2	someValuesFrom	2	
Incorrect Decomposition	3	equivalentClass	1	
		subClassOf	1	
		someValuesFrom	1	
Newly Added Information	4	subClassOf	2	
		-	2	
Model Laziness - does not spell out everything	1	equivalentClass	1	
Llama 3	Concept renamed	18	subClassOf	17
			-	1
	Newly Added Information	39	subClassOf	16
			disjointWith	5
			equivalentClass	2
			-	16
	Relationship with missing value	17	someValuesFrom	17
	Missing Relationship - Relationship that was completely omitted	24	allValuesFrom	7
			subClassOf	7
			equivalentClass	5
			disjointWith	2
			-	3
	Replacement of relationship with a another relationship that has the same meaning	11	disjointWith	4
hasValue			3	
subClassOf			2	
someValuesFrom			2	
Incorrect Decompositon	5	someValuesFrom	2	
		subClassOf	2	
		equivalentClass	1	
Incorrect Paraphrasing	2	subClassOf	2	
Model Lazyness - does not spell out everything	7	-	7	